

Appendix 1. Data typing for the metamodels

In this appendix, we present a generalized data-typing scheme required for a potential software implementation of the metamodels. Data typing is introduced to control and validate the appropriate input of data for each profile.

We consider the following assignments for each model:

- User model (UM): $GA = UA$, $ga = ua$ and $GM = UM$
- User context model (UCM): $GA = CA$, $ga = ca$ and $GM = UCM$
- Web interface model (WIM): $GA = WIA$, $ga = wia$ and $GM = WIM$
- Web browsing behavior model (UBM): $GA = UBA$, $ga = uba$ and $GM = UBM$

To ensure that typing is consistent (i.e., each attribute has a unique type), we require:

$$\forall ga \in GA, \exists! dataType \in DataTypeName: (ga, dataType) \in GM \quad (1)$$

Where $ga \in \Sigma^*$ denotes the attribute name (identifier) and $DataType \in \Sigma^*$ denotes the name of the data type associated with the attribute.

The symbol $DataType$ is used to specify the data type of each attribute. This typing is intended for software implementation purposes, in order to control and validate the appropriate input of data for the user profile. To this end, we start from the definition of a catalog of data types that attributes may assume, as stated in the following definition:

$$DataTypeAttribute \subseteq DataTypeName \times ConcreteDataType \quad (2)$$

Where $DataTypeName$ is the name of the data type and $ConcreteDataType$ represents the concrete type associated with $DataTypeName$. In this work, we consider two families of types: basic and enumerated. Therefore:

$$ConcreteDataType = BasicDataType \cup ListDataType \quad (3)$$

Additionally, every type name used in the model must exist in the $DataTypeAttribute$ catalog:

$$\forall (ga, dataType) \in GM, \exists! dt \in concreteDataType: (dataType, dt) \in dataTypeAttribute \quad (4)$$

Basic data types ($BasicDataType$) are those commonly used in computing to define variables that store numeric, textual, or logical values, such as integer, float, string, etc. Formally:

$$BasicDataType = \{Integer, Float, String, Boolean, Date, \dots\} \quad (5)$$

In contrast, enumerated data types ($ListDataType$) are defined by a finite list of options. In this work, they are represented as pairs $(EnumName, Values)$, where $EnumName$ identifies the enumeration and $Values \subseteq \Sigma^*$ is the set of admissible values:

$$ListDataType = \{(EnumName, Values) \mid EnumName \in \Sigma^*, Values \subseteq \Sigma^*\} \quad (6)$$

For example, an enumerated data type for representing the user's gender may be named "GenderType" and include values such as "Male", "Female", and "Prefer not to say".

Note: These data-type definitions apply both to user attributes and to attributes of the other profiles proposed in this work.